

Common Infrastructure for National Cohorts in Europe, Canada, and Africa - CINECA -

Deliverable D6.1

Outreach and dissemination plan

WP6 - Outreach, training and dissemination

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1 Executive summary

In this deliverable document, we report on the activities in task 6.1 - Stakeholder analysis, with the outreach and dissemination plan, as well as the training plan presented in this report, we have completed this task. We have used a combination of surveys and face-to-face meetings to verify and extend or identify key stakeholder groups, understand their interest in the project, and identify bottlenecks that can be addressed by outreach and training. Outreach activities will be accomplished by task 6.2 and training by task 6.3.

The stakeholder survey was developed and distributed within the CINECA stakeholder community; a total of 54 responses were received. While the response rate was on the low side, it is sufficient for the initial analysis, which is presented below. A CINECA competency framework was developed and validated through the survey. The competency framework has four areas of competence (generating data, finding and accessing data, analysis and clinical interpretation of data and sharing data), reflecting the research lifecycle. A total of 17 competencies have been defined. We consider both the stakeholder analysis and the competency profile to be living documents that will evolve over the course of the project. We plan to obtain additional feedback on both the competency profile as well as update the stakeholder analysis throughout the project through a range of methods, these could include interviews, discussion groups, conference workshops.

A dissemination strategy was created aimed at the effective communication of CINECA activities and outcomes to all relevant partners and stakeholders. To this end, a range of dissemination channels have been set up, including a CINECA project webpage, various social media channels, a newsletter, and physical materials such as flyers and brochures. Furthermore, a set of conferences and events have been identified at which a CINECA presence (e.g. workshop, booth, talk) could benefit stakeholder engagement. Consistent branding across these different dissemination channels is achieved through the development of a logo, colour scheme, and the creation of templates for materials such as brochures, posters and slides. Furthermore, a number of CINECA areas of research and expertise have been identified that may be suitable for publication as peer-reviewed articles.

A training plan was developed covering a variety of learning interventions, including webinars, staff visits, workshops and hackathons. In the early phase of the project (first ~18 months), training activities will be focused primarily on internal CINECA knowledge exchanges to allow work package interdependencies to be resolved. To this end, a regular webinar series has been started to inform CINECA project members and other interested parties of the various CINECA activities and outcomes. Furthermore, a staff exchange program was set up to allow knowledge exchanges between different interdependent work packages. CINECA members may submit staff visit requests via an online form, and after the visit a blog post about the outcomes will be posted on the CINECA website. As the project progresses, the focus of training activities will gradually shift to dissemination to a wider audience and will consist primarily of workshops (face-to-face or online) and hackathons.

2 Project objectives

With this deliverable, the project has contributed to the following objectives:

- a) To raise awareness of CINECA and the opportunities and challenges of sharing cohort data on a global scale, building relationships with related projects
- b) To disseminate the results produced by CINECA through social media channels, blogs, international meetings and publications.
- c) To identify and address training needs by identifying existing learning opportunities and creating new ones – both within the consortium itself and more broadly

3 Introduction

WP6: “Outreach Dissemination and Training” covers a set of activities that aim to develop and deliver training (or other learning interventions e.g. secondments; communities of practice; hackathons) that integrate the outputs of the technical work packages to deliver the project’s training goals. It also has the task of raising awareness of the project’s goals and outcomes through diverse dissemination channels and activities.

4 Stakeholder and needs analysis

4.1 Stakeholder survey

The stakeholder survey was developed with input from across the CINECA work packages. The survey was distributed among the stakeholders identified in the first 3 months of the project. A workshop was held at IHCC (International Hundred Thousand Cohorts Consortium meeting in Reykjavik in April 2019) to disseminate the survey, gather preliminary stakeholder input, as well as promote general CINECA awareness.

The survey received 54 responses, 10 respondents did not answer the first consent question, 2 responses were disqualified as they did not consent to the data sharing policy, and of the remaining 42 responses, 32 were incomplete or partial responses. The completion rate was not as high as we had hoped for. As stated in the risk register, our mitigation strategy was to perform an additional round of dissemination, as well as discuss ways to further increase response rates. While the response rate was on the low side, it is sufficient for the initial analysis. We plan to obtain additional validation of the results through other means (e.g. interviews, discussion groups, conference workshops) throughout the project. The stakeholder map will evolve over time and re-analysis of the results will take place after verification has occurred and further stakeholder responses have been received. We consider both the stakeholder analysis and the competency profile to be living documents that will evolve over the course of the project. The CINECA competency profile will be added to the EMBL-EBI competency mapper (<https://competency.ebi.ac.uk/>), where we can maintain stable versions of the profile. It is worth noting that additional data and valuable input into the stakeholder analysis was obtained at IHCC.

Who answered the survey

The responses we received were predominantly from people based in European institutes, though 20% came from African institutes and 13% from Canadian institutes.

Figure 1: geographical breakdown of host institutes of the survey respondents

The WP8 subtask 8.1.3 - Development and Implementation of benefit-sharing plan for lower middle-income countries/South Africa will ensure that the local research needs in South Africa are taken into account and training, scientific excellence and knowledge exchange with South Africa are equally addressed throughout the consortium.

To further understand the respondents of the survey and our stakeholder community, the survey respondents were asked whether they self-identify with a set list of groups (Cohort manager, Researchers/clinical practitioners using cohort data, Industrial researcher using cohort data, Service provider, Staff of funding bodies/organisations, Policy makers, General public, Patient groups, cohort members, charities and other (please specify)). Respondents were allowed to select multiple options.

Figure 2: stakeholder groups of the survey respondents

We have had representation across the identified stakeholders groups, with the largest group of respondents (56%) identifying themselves as “Researchers/clinical practitioners using cohort data” and 38% each for “cohort manager” and “service provider”. For the “Other” option, respondents mentioned Principal Investigator, Management of NGS data and projects, and ELSI researcher.

We were interested in knowing which of the CINECA cohorts/resources are most relevant to the respondents research, the results are given below.

Figure 3: CINECA cohorts/resources relevance to the survey respondents

Other cohorts and tools that were specifically mentioned are: cohort network LifeCycle and EUCAN-Connect, ICGC (<https://dcc.icgc.org/>), Hartwig Medical Foundation metastatic cancer (4000 WGS), and BBMRI Directory. Cohorts represented at IHCC, that provided input but were not previously mentioned.

The respondents and the CINECA project

We asked the respondents “How do you hope to interact with the CINECA project”, this will allow us to tailor out dissemination instruments and training interventions appropriately. A total number of 12 valid responses were received through the survey.

Figure 4: Survey respondents interaction with CINECA

In an additional survey question “If you could choose only one, what would be your preferred training format?” aimed to analyse the preferred training format, “attend short face-to-face training events” and “watch webinars and short videos on relevant topics” were equally popular.

Bottlenecks to analysing your cohort data

To appropriately target the CINECA training interventions, we are very keen to understand the bottlenecks scientists face to analysing their cohort data. In total we received 23 valid statements to the question “What are the major bottlenecks to analysing your cohort data?”. The question was asked both at the IHCC registration as well as during the CINECA survey. We have removed statements such as ‘not applicable’, ‘to follow’, ‘too early to say’ etc.

We clustered the statements according to the following themes, statements can be scored in more than one theme, but will only be added once to each theme even if different sub-themes have been mentioned explicitly.

Themes identified:

- **Accessibility:** Accessibility of data, this includes speed of access, stable connectivity for transferring large datasets, data access procedures, unwillingness to share data
- **Data Analysis environment:** Lack of data analysis environment
- **Patient volume:** Patient volumes
- **Data:** Data gaps, data harmonisation and curation, quality control of data, lack of validation data
- **Funding:** a specific mention of lack of monetary funding
- **Skilled workers:** a specific mention of lack of manpower or specifically skilled people

Figure 5: Data analysis bottlenecks for the survey respondents

4.2 Training needs analysis

The results from the stakeholder survey feed into the training needs analysis and will be used to inform the delivery of training, or other learning interventions, to fill training gaps. This work will be done in collaboration with WPs 1-5 and 7, with each of these work packages contributing to the development and delivery of training. At the beginning of the project we will need to train our consortium members. However, as the project progresses and the project develops solutions, the emphasis will change to focus on key stakeholder groups external to the project. The majority of our efforts will be targeted at this group.

The delivery mechanism of new training will be tailored to the specific needs and driven by carefully defined competencies required by the audience. Training needs within the project are likely to be fulfilled by staff visits, webinars, hackathons or other knowledge exchange activities in which the project consortium members are experts.

To inform the development of the CINECA training programme, WP6, with the input of the CINECA consortium partners, and through the training needs analysis gathered the competency requirements of CINECA community (internal and external), in other words, define the competencies that users of CINECA need to develop, to enable them to fully exploit the applications provided by the project. Subsequently we have mapped these competencies to the learning outcomes of courses already provided by existing training programmes so that we can perform a gap analysis that will highlight significant gaps in training and thereby help us focus on developing new training that meets currently unmet needs.

A Competency is an observable ability of any professional, integrating multiple components such as knowledge, skills and behaviours.

The key aspects of the competency-based approach are:

- Competencies are observable, so acquisition can be validated objectively
- Evidence of competency can be collected in a competency portfolio
- Competencies are shared 'currency' applicable to learning of all types and at all career stages

We have defined a CINECA competency framework that has the following broad areas of competence (see figure 6).

Figure 6: CINECA competency framework

Each of the areas build on each other and competence in each area strengthens the competence in the subsequent area. The areas of competency follow the research lifecycle.

For the underlying competencies, a number of previously existing competency frameworks have been used (CORBEL, BioExcel, EDISON, ISCB, NHS Clinical Bioinformatics). Across the 4 areas there are a total of 17 competencies; 5 competencies in generating data, 2 additional competencies in Finding and accessing data, 7 in Analysing and clinical interpretation of data and 3 in sharing your data. At this point in time, the CINECA competency profile does not have Knowledge, Skills and Attitudes (KSAs). KSAs are a common and useful way to further divide and clarify competencies. A number of the competency frameworks that were used to create already have KSAs or (CORBEL, BioExcel, EDISON, ISCB, NHS Clinical Bioinformatics) or are in the process of drafting KSAs. See the full competency profile below.

In the stakeholder and needs analysis survey we presented the CINECA competency profile to the respondents and asked them whether competency in the areas presented was important for their own professional development/activities and for their organisation. The responses are given in the table below (Table 1), alongside the CINECA Competency Framework, though it should be noted that the results are based on a low number of valid answers so have a large margin of error.

The top areas important for professional development and respondents organisation are listed in table 2 and table 3.

CINECA Competency framework	Important to you for your professional development/ activities?*	Important for your organisation?*
Generating data		

Apply expertise in medical science, clinical genomics, drug discovery, health care appropriate to the discipline	60%	90%
Apply expertise in formal & natural sciences appropriate to the discipline.	0%	10%
Detailed comprehension of the scientific process and an ability to apply it (e.g. experimental design; inclusion of controls; QA, QC, processing, visualisation and interpretation of results).	30%	40%
Data interoperability (metadata, ontologies, standards, harmonization of metadata); FAIR principles	50%	70%
Data management/preservation/curation	70%	80%
Finding and accessing data		
Identify, access and compile relevant data sets from multiple publicly available sources (e.g. databases, literature), and requesting access to sensitive and confidential data	60%	70%
Ethical, legal and social implications of clinical use of genomic data (including issues surrounding identification of patients, clinical benefits and risks, patient consent, incidental findings and ethical implications of unexpected clinically actionable findings)	70%	80%
Analysing and clinical interpretation of data		
Analyse genomics/multiomics data using pre-existing software, including linking genotype to phenotype	63%	50%
Interpret genetic variation in a clinical context, including understanding limitations of analysis, assessing quality and evidence for clinical interpretation	88%	70%
Define Computing requirements appropriate to solve a given scientific problem (e.g., system, process, algorithm, component or program; define algorithmic time and space complexities and hardware resources required to solve a problem).	38%	30%
Statistical research methods in the context of molecular biology, genomics, medical, and population genetics research.	63%	50%
Install software on personal computer/cloud/grid/HPC environment as applicable	38%	40%
Deploy and test non-commercial software, including software that is built collaboratively and on a volunteer basis. Employ good software development practices	25%	30%

Apply knowledge of systems monitoring (e.g. queue monitoring, systems availability and optimisation, storage used; scheduling maintenance at appropriate times and communicating this to users).	25%	50%
Sharing your data		
Data security practices, including accreditation and standards (e.g. ISO 9000, ISO 13485, ISO 20387)	90%	70%
The role of various types of healthcare professional in genomic medicine	40%	60%
Service design, including identification and understanding of user needs	50%	50%

* Source: Survey questions "Competency in which of the following areas is important to you for your professional development/activities?" and "Competency in which of the following areas is important to you for your professional development/activities?". Note that the results are based on a low number of valid answers so have a large margin of error.

Table 1: CINECA Competency framework

The top areas for professional development:

Area	Competency	Percentage
Sharing your data	Data security practices, including accreditation and standards (e.g. ISO 9000, ISO 13485, ISO 20387)	90%
Analysing and clinical interpretation of data	Interpret genetic variation in a clinical context, including understanding limitations of analysis, assessing quality and evidence for clinical interpretation	88%
Generating data	Data management/preservation/curation	70%
Finding and accessing data	Ethical, legal and social implications of clinical use of genomic data (including issues surrounding identification of patients, clinical benefits and risks, patient consent, incidental findings and ethical implications of unexpected clinically actionable findings)	70%
Analysing and clinical interpretation of data	Analyse genomics/multiomics data using pre-existing software, including linking genotype to phenotype	63%
Analysing and clinical interpretation of data	Statistical research methods in the context of molecular biology, genomics, medical, and population genetics research.	63%

Table 2: Top areas of professional development

The top areas for your organisation:

Area	Competency	Percentage
Generating data	Apply expertise in medical science, clinical genomics, drug discovery, health care appropriate to the discipline	90%
Generating data	Data management/preservation/curation	80%
Finding and accessing data	Ethical, legal and social implications of clinical use of genomic data (including issues surrounding identification of patients, clinical benefits and risks, patient consent, incidental findings and ethical implications of unexpected clinically actionable findings)	80%
Generating data	Data interoperability (metadata, ontologies, standards, harmonization of metadata); FAIR principles	70%
Finding and accessing data	Identify, access and compile relevant data sets from multiple publicly available sources (e.g. databases, literature), and requesting access to sensitive and confidential data	70%
Analysing and clinical interpretation of data	Interpret genetic variation in a clinical context, including understanding limitations of analysis, assessing quality and evidence for clinical interpretation	70%
Sharing your data	Data security practices, including accreditation and standards (e.g. ISO 9000, ISO 13485, ISO 20387)	70%

Table 3: Top areas of organisation

5 Dissemination overview

5.1 Dissemination goal

The overall goal of CINECA's outreach and dissemination plan is to ensure that relevant information about/from the project is available and delivered to all partners and stakeholders with wide reaching and effective impact. It must therefore be ensured that CINECA activities and materials are extensively distributed and promoted within the research community, in industry and society as a whole, and that the project's benefits are widely communicated via appropriate channels and fully grasped by its target audience. Therefore, this plan will also ensure that CINECA outcomes are communicated and transferred to appropriate stakeholders through training and education activities. This plan shall be made available in a suitable and accessible format from M9 until the end of the project.

This plan will be proposed by WP6 and has to be accepted by all the partners of the project. WP6 will be responsible for the dissemination of CINECA objectives and outcomes from all work package deliverables to appropriate stakeholders. To this end, WP6 will closely work with each of the WP

leaders to plan and monitor the dissemination of the publication of results, workshops, hackathons, webinars, news and project progress in the different WPs.

5.2 Dissemination strategy

Given the large stakeholder group expected to benefit from CINECA project's outputs, we will leverage the existing communications plans and strategies of ELIXIR, BBMRI, GA4GH and H3Africa by aligning our outreach and dissemination strategy with theirs. This will also enable the support of CINECA's outputs after funding for CINECA is complete as these organisations will still continue to exist. Because of the importance of this plan as one of the strong components of the project that will promote the project's results and demonstrate its impact, all the partners will need to participate in training and dissemination activities proposed in this outreach and dissemination plan, and contribute to delivering the project's output to international and diverse stakeholders. The implementation of this outreach and dissemination plan should deliver high visibility for the project and ensure that the outputs of the project are highly accessed and utilised.

Each WP will deliver materials for dissemination and training activities, which will be coordinated and delivered by WP6 ensuring that:

- the project communication strategy is instantiated as a rolling and responsive communication plan aligned with that of ELIXIR, BBMRI, GA4GH and H3Africa
- the dissemination plan is targeted at the scientific community in the form of papers, presentations at scientific meetings, as well as short videos and webinars
- a close engagement of end users for the project's technical outputs across academia, SMEs and large industry
- a strategic engagement with funders, policy makers, international standards organisations
- the design and delivery of the project's exploitation strategy

5.3 Dissemination timetable

Deliverable	Responsibility	Partner involved	Comments
Stakeholder and needs analysis	UCT, EMBL-EBI	EMC	Completed
Dissemination plan	UCT	EMBL-EBI, EMC	The dissemination plan will be updated ongoing
Training plan	EMBL-EBI, EMC	UCT	The training plan will be updated ongoing
Logo	EMBL-EBI		Completed
Project website	UCT	EMBL-EBI, EMC	Ongoing since M6
Newsletters	EMBL-EBI	UCT, EMC	Start in M10

Materials for social media feeds	EMBL-EBI	All partners	Ongoing since M6
Training materials	EMBL-EBI	All partners	Start in M12
Report on dissemination activities	UCT, EMBL-EBI, EMC	All partners	Ongoing

Table 4: CINECA dissemination timetable

5.4 Target groups and key messages

CINECA has the potential to impact a wide group of stakeholders spanning from academia, industry, the public sector and charities. These stakeholders include the researchers leading and implementing international cohort projects; cohort participants; clinical practitioners working with cohort participants to translate genomics research into clinical decisions; those managing the data and metadata collected; those providing the systems that enable this collection, the funders of such projects and others providing related education and outreach. These stakeholders will require effective and targeted dissemination activities to be able to adopt and effectively implement the results of CINECA projects.

[Table 5](#) lists all stakeholder groups with associated strategic objectives, communication message, and tools and process for dissemination.

Target group	Strategic Objective	Message	Process and Tools
Consortium	Raise awareness of the project.		Mailing lists, meeting attendance, website, social media feeds, newsletter
Biomedical Scientific Community	Raise awareness of the project. Ensure scientific results have a high impact. Promote scientific collaboration.	Novel scientific outputs based on cross cohort analyses, infrastructure integration and federated data access mechanisms.	National and international workshops, training events, website, newsletter, mailing lists, meeting attendance, social media feeds, (shared) booth/sponsorship of events e.g. ELIXIR booths with CINECA documentation.

Technical end users	<p>Share technical strategy with the national and institutional user community.</p> <p>Solve community technical challenges.</p> <p>Drive technology development for use by project.</p> <p>Promote technical collaboration.</p>	<p>Novel technical outputs addressing cohort level data access and integration challenges suitable for cloud deployment.</p> <p>Open cutting-edge technical development using international standards with accessible code in open code repositories.</p>	<p>Technical discussion forums.</p> <p>Technical training events.</p>
Funders	<p>Deliver funding impact statements for project outputs.</p> <p>Raise awareness of the project</p> <p>Inclusion of project outputs in funder strategies.</p>	<p>Importance of cross cohort analyses on path to personalised medicine.</p> <p>Tangible healthcare outputs.</p>	<p>Engagement in funder strategy development via expert communities, via coordinated responses to RFIs, via BMS RI's and partner funder engagement.</p>
Policy makers	<p>Raise awareness of project outputs.</p> <p>Identification of policy challenges for the project.</p>	<p>Project outputs implementing international and national policy.</p>	<p>Via international policy forums e.g. GA4GH.</p>
Standards organisations	<p>Raise awareness of the project.</p> <p>Disseminate practical approaches to implementation.</p> <p>Drive standards development.</p>	<p>Use of standards and development of extensions and enhancements to existing standards.</p>	<p>Via engagement with standards developers, to contribute directly to standards development e.g. Research Data Alliance.</p>
Industry	<p>Raise awareness of the project.</p> <p>Promote industrial collaboration.</p>	<p>Innovative cohort level analyses and infrastructure development.</p>	<p>Via IMI, via SME fora, via EMBL-EBI industry forum and training programmes. Via BBMRI and ELIXIR industry engagement.</p>

General public, patient groups, cohort members, charities.	Promote scientific outputs Promote the importance of international collaboration.	Importance of large scale and diverse studies. Data security measures Impact on healthcare.	Press releases, press conferences, project expert placement in media information organisations, videos.
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Table 5: Summary of pre-identified stakeholder groups, message and processes for communication

5.5 Dissemination tools and channels

The use of appropriate dissemination channels and tools will be critical to ensuring a wide and effective communication of knowledge, processes, blockers and achievements of the project within and outside the project, to partners and stakeholders all around the globe. Electronic and printed media will be adopted to deliver the project messages to this diverse audience. Appropriate channels including webinars, seminars, conferences, social media and newsletters will be used to reach all target groups and to maximise the impact of CINECA both internally and externally.

Each tool has to take into consideration the contractual obligation to add the EU logo https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/grants/grant-management/acknowledge-funding_en.htm

5.5.1 Branding

This section describes the design of all graphic elements that will be included in all project's communication materials and channels including the definition of the project logo, colour palette, fonts, tagline, banners for acknowledgements for EU and Canada, templates for presentation and reporting, letterheads and infographics that will make up the project identity.

Logo

The conception of the logo underwent multiple stages including proposal of few visual designs, selection and redesign of some of the selected ones, and final selection through vote among all project partners. The approved logo is available in different formats and sizes (coloured, black and white, vector, print, web). A colour palette has thus been derived from the project logo, which will be used in all subsequent branding and communication materials.

Figure 7. Project logo and colour palette

All communication materials, deliverables, milestones and reports produced by the project during its lifetime will be branded with the CINECA logo.

Templates

Presentation slide templates have been proposed in collaboration with WP8, which contain both the project logo and acknowledgement of the project funders. The templates are proposed in the two formats (4:3-standard and 16:9-widescreen) for different potential internal and external usages.

Figure 8. Slide template for presentation on the 16:9-widescreen (top) and 4:3-standard (bottom) formats

Posters

A poster template with all project graphic elements is proposed for use at conferences for general project presentation. The poster design should be consistent with the graphic elements to promote the project branding.

Figure 9. Template for poster presentation

Brochures

Printed brochures will be used at conferences to showcase the project and serve as a promotional document to inform prospective attendees. An example of a brochure is displayed below.

Figure 10. Example of a tentative CINECA brochure

Flyers

Flyers will be designed to promote events, with the paper version to be distributed at public places and online copies to be attached with social media posts.

Figure 11. Example of a tentative CINECA flyer

5.5.2 Website

The website is a fundamental tool for internal communication as well for interaction with the public. Thus, a considerable effort will be made to ensure that the website presents the project information in a manner that is easily understood by the public.

The website design started in M4 and will be finalised in M12, with continued content updates until the end of the project. The creation process began with preliminary discussions between WP6 with EBI-EMBL web development team about technical requirements of the website. This was followed by various interactions within WP6 website task team lead by UCT regarding the structure of the website and relevant contents. A review process was undertaken with considerable feedback from the website task team and followed by contributions from the rest of the consortium. The project's website <https://www.cineca-project.eu> was launched on 6th June 2019.

The website uses Squarespace (<https://www.squarespace.com/>) as a content management system and for hosting. Squarespace provides an all-in-one solution to easily and quickly build a modern website. The website was designed with a layout that would make it user friendly, easy to find relevant project content and as interactive as possible in order to facilitate high level engagement with the user. Thus, the website will contain interactive graphical elements, cross-referencing and preview from project social media Twitter and YouTube accounts, and frequent updates in forms of news and events, project outputs, publications and other produced materials such as such training materials, and much more. The website should present relevant information about the project, highly summarised and concise, maintaining a high-level comprehensible language to make the website content readable to all target audiences, including stakeholders and the general public.

The website is structured in a modern layout based on a landing page with 4 menu sections, which can be navigated through a simple page scrolling without the need for numerous clicks by the user to access content. Page subsections are also directly accessible from the top horizontal menu, allowing the user to easily find any relevant content on the website. The general architecture and content of the website is illustrated in Table 6 below.

Section	Subsections	Contents
Home		<p>Top part - all visible without scrolling</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Header with infographic illustrating the overall idea of the project, including: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Project tagline summarising the goal of the project. ○ Interactive world map with dots on each project partners. The name and location of thee partner is displayed on mouse hover. ○ Overall description of consortium's cohort. ● Just below: List of the five main challenges/objectives of the project. <p>Following parts -- visible by scrolling down</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Recent news and events including latest articles, past and upcoming events such as webinars, workshops.

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Band with scrolling list of partner logos ● Footer: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Project contact email address ○ Project social media channel (Twitter, Youtube, LinkedIn) ○ Band with some quick links to most visited sections of the website. ○ acknowledgment banners; ○ copyright and privacy policy.
About CINECA	History	Project rationale and objectives.
	Partners	List of partners with links to each partner description page with brief description, logo, country, website link and a contact person.
	Cohorts	List of participating cohorts with links to each cohort description page and main features such as sample size, data types, location, etc.
	Related projects	List and short description of analogous research initiatives in EU and Canada and those funded under the same H2020 call.
How we work	Governance	High-level organisational structure of the project.
	Work packages	High-level implementation structure, with brief descriptions of main work package.
Dissemination	News & Events	Including meetings, press releases, webinars, workshops, general assembly
	Webinars	Subset of 'News & Events' with a focus on webinars only
	Blog	Blog posts from anything CINECA related i.e. meeting reports, public deliverables, success stories, partner posts, etc.
Impact	Scientific impact	Description of the project scientific outputs.

Table 6: General architecture and content of the CINECA website

This series of preview images illustrates the actual website design as it is being developed (Figure 7-9). The content of the website is also under review by the consortium partners. Some additional sections/pages will be added as the website contents become available during the project's lifetime.

Homepage

Common Infrastructure for National Cohorts in Europe, Canada, and Africa

HOME ABOUT CINECA HOW WE WORK DISSEMINATION IMPACT SEARCH

Events | Contacts

Accelerating disease research and improving health by facilitating transcontinental human data exchange

Cohort Types and Volumes

- ~1.4M Participants
- 13 Cohorts
- 3 Continents
- Longitudinal, Disease: 9 700
- Disease: 75 450
- Longitudinal, Population, Disease: 700 000
- Population: 4 000

Services: Federated Data Discovery, Authentication & Authorisation, Harmonised Metadata, Federated Data Analysis, ELSI Framework

Latest from CINECA

May 29, 2019

CINECA stakeholder engagement session at IHCC

CINECA organised its first stakeholder engagement session at the International Cohorts Summit held in Reykjavik, Iceland in April 2019.

[Read More →](#)

Upcoming Events

Past Webinars

The CINECA project - Addressing bottlenecks in cohort data analysis
Jun 6, 2019 · Webinars

OUR PARTNERS

- Erasmus MC
- SIB Swiss Institute of Bioinformatics
- SickKids THE HOSPITAL FOR SICK CHILDREN
- BBMRI-ERIC® Biobanking and BioMolecular resources Research Infrastructure
- ClinicaGeno

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Figure 7: CINECA website homepage preview

Partners page

The consortium involves 18 full partners from 10 different countries across three continents. The partners are world-class leaders in their fields, with long-standing experience in translation of research results into diagnostic applications. The collection of partners has representation from key European and international standards organisations, as well as industry SMEs. As representatives of major informatics resources and organisations we have the ability to deliver CINECA's objectives robustly and at scale driving the academic, SME and health infrastructures forward.

This partnership has investment in, and access to, both molecular and phenotypic data available from a diverse and impactful set of cohorts corresponding to 1.4 million individuals. We currently operate the state of the art infrastructures, analyses, knowledge discovery and data discovery platforms on which we will build to deliver our vision of a federated solution enabling **population scale genomic and biomolecular data accessible across international borders accelerating research and improving the health of individuals resident across continents**.

COMPLETE LIST OF CINECA PARTNERS

Institute name	Short name	Country
Biobanking and Biomolecular resources Research Infrastructure - European Research Infrastructure Consortium	BBMRI-ERIC	Austria
Centre for Genomic Regulation	CRG	Spain
Clinicageno Limited	Clinicageno	United Kingdom
ERASMUS University Medical Centre Rotterdam	EMC	Netherlands
European Molecular Biology Laboratory, European Bioinformatics Institute	EMBL-EBI	United Kingdom
IT Center for Science	CSC	Finland
Masaryk University	MU	Czech Republic
National Institute for Health and Medical Research	INSERM	France
Royal Institution for the Advancement of Learning, McGill University	MCG	Canada
SIB Swiss Institute of Bioinformatics	SIB	Switzerland
Simon Fraser University	SFU	Canada
The Chancellor, Masters and Scholars of the University of Oxford	UOXF	United Kingdom
The Hospital for Sick Children	SickKids	Canada

Figure 8: CINECA website partners preview

Partner page

GROUP LEADER: THOMAS KEANE

EMBL European Molecular Biology Laboratory

The European Bioinformatics Institute (EMBL-EBI) is part of the European Molecular Biology Laboratory (EMBL), a non-profit, intergovernmental organisation funded by 24 member states and two associate member states. Our 570 staff deliver services, research and training to an international user community and form the largest centre for bioinformatics in Europe. EMBL-EBI provides access to biological data via core informatics resources such as Ensembl, UniProt, Europe PubMedCentral and the European Genome-phenotype Archive (EGA) which we deliver in collaboration with the Centre For Genomic Regulation (CRG). We participate in international infrastructure design, delivery and best practice through ELIXIR, GA4GH and are funded to deliver internationally important infrastructural services via the CORBEL, EXCELERATE and Accelerating Medicines Partnership T2D projects.

Country: United Kingdom
Website: <https://www.ebi.ac.uk>

Figure 11: CINECA website single partner page preview

Work packages page

At a high level, CINECA will be structured into six implementation steps, which will build toward a unified platform for cohort level federated genetic discovery and analysis:

- **WP1 (Federated Data Discovery and Querying) interconnections with WP2, 3, 4, 5.** WP2 will utilise the AAI services provided by WP2 through ELIXIR (Europe) and CanDIG (Canada) infrastructures. WP1 will use the phenotype semantic harmonisation from WP3 as the basis for carrying out federated phenotype driven data discovery. WP1 partners will implement the handoff service to transition from the discovery service (WP1) to doing federated analysis (WP4) on discovered cohorts.
- **WP2 (Interoperable Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure) interconnections with WP1, 4, 5.** The AAI services provided by WP2 via the ELIXIR and CanDIG AAI service will ensure that all requests for cohort data for discovery (WP1), federated analysis (WP4), and clinical applications (WP5) are correctly authenticated and authorised. Importantly WP2 will provide AAI interoperability between Canada, Europe, and Africa cohort infrastructures and researchers.
- **WP3 (Cohort Level Metadata Representation) interconnections with WP1, 4, 5.** The cross cohort harmonised metadata and machine readable data use ontologies will be used by WP1 to provide structured data discovery services across the federated cohort network.
- **WP4 (Federated Joint Cohort Analysis) interconnections with WP1, 2, 3.** WP4 will draw upon the cumulative services of almost all of the other WPs, e.g. data discovery (WP1), researcher AAI (WP2), and harmonised metadata (WP3) to form the input for the federated analysis applications. When data analysis is complete it will be submitted to EGA for data sharing, prior to this it will be available within the consortium as a series of shared, cloud based workflows, hosted on the EMBL-EBI Embassy cloud.
- **WP5 (Healthcare Interoperability and Clinical Applications) interconnections with WP1, 2, 3, 4.** WP5 will build clinical applications and tools that will use the services from all of the technical work packages (WP1-4) and the ELSI framework (WP7) and data sharing model (WP4).
- **WP6 (Outreach Dissemination and Training) interconnections with WP 1, 2, 3, 4, 5.** Develop and deliver training (or other learning interventions e.g. secondments; communities of practice; hackathons) that integrate the outputs of the technical work packages to deliver the project's training goals.
- **WP7 (Ethical and legal governance framework for transnational data-sharing) interconnections with WP1, 2, 5, 6.** WP7 will collaborate in particular with WP1 (Federated data discovery and querying), WP2 (Researcher identities and authorisations as personal data under EU GDPR and Canadian Privacy Act and PIPEDA), and the provincial variants FOIPPA and FIPPA) to analyse the landscape of ethical and legal policies and their implications for intensified inter-continental data sharing between Europe, Canada, and Africa.

Figure 12: CINECA website work packages page preview

Contacts page

Figure 13: CINECA website contacts page preview

5.5.3 Newsletters

Newsletters are an important marketing tool which will be used to inform readers about upcoming events, webinars and activities within the project. Developing a mailing list will assist in maintaining ongoing connections with our partners and readers. We plan to send the first newsletter during autumn 2019.

5.5.4 Social Media Channels

Having a strong social media strategy will assist with brand awareness and marketing opportunities. The following channels will be used to disseminate information about the goals of the project.

- Twitter - <https://twitter.com/cinecaproject>
- LinkedIn - <https://www.linkedin.com/company/cineca-project>
- YouTube - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=GbRkJZEzjUM&t=219s>

The social media strategy will be coordinated with all partners within the consortium, as well as with relevant partners outside of the consortium such as ELIXIR and other related EU projects under the same CINECA's grant.

Twitter

The CINECA twitter account is the primary dissemination channel. Twitter impressions is a useful metric to determine the reach of a post. Since January 2019, the account has 197 followers and generates an average of 9,400 impressions per month. Below are examples of top tweets with a high number of impressions.

Figure 13: Snapshot of the CINECA Twitter page

LinkedIn

The LinkedIn account currently has 14 followers and is used to market events in a professional context.

Figure 14: Snapshot of the CINECA LinkedIn page

YouTube

The CINECA project YouTube channel was launched in June 2019 which is utilised to host recorded webinars.

Figure 15: CINECA YouTube page

5.5.5 Publications

Project outcomes concerning this research and innovation project's design, processes and outputs both during and subsequent to funding end will be published in peer reviewed journals. During the review phase, preprints of papers may also be offered to promote early access and community use of our outputs. Publications will be open access and will be linked to ORCID's for ease of tracking via the AAI implementation in WP2.

The following areas of scientific endeavour are targeted for peer review papers:

- A discovery API for cohort data
- Results of federated analyses of cohort data
- Common Data model for cohort data metadata
- Data harmonisation and curatorial toolkit for cohort data
- Bioinformatics interoperability toolkit for cohort data
- Data Use Ontology for machine readable data access

Best practice and white papers in the following areas are expected to be published:

- Challenges of data integration across international cohorts
- Security best practice for federated data sharing of international cohort data
- Best practice in harmonisation strategies for longitudinal and disease specific cohorts
- Training strategies for cohort data integration and analyses
- Cultural and technical challenges in data sharing across continents
- Ethical best practice for cohort data sharing across continents and legal jurisdictions

5.6 Events

CINECA events including conferences, webinars, workshops, as well as external events attended by CINECA partners or any events involving any of CINECA's activities or outcomes will be announced on the website, in the newsletter and on social media networks. Event materials such as articles, reports, photos, posters, speaker notes should be submitted to the dissemination management team at info@cineca-project.eu, to be presented in articles that can be published on the website and promoted on social media.

CINECA events will be targeting the different pre-identified groups of stakeholders and will be carried throughout the project lifetime. Dissemination of CINECA training opportunities will be carried out using the appropriate channels in close coordination with other WPs.

5.6.1 Conferences

Existing conferences were surveyed and those potentially beneficial to the project were selected. The project representation at these high-profile meetings will provide an important opportunity for additional dissemination. Targeted international conferences are listed in Table 7 below.

Date	Meeting	Location
October 15-19, 2019	American Society of Human Genetics conference	Houston, USA
May 4-5, 2020	IHCC	Santiago, Chile
June 6-9, 2020	The European Human Genetics Conference	Berlin, Germany
July 12-16, 2020	ISMB (Co -hosted with ELIXIR)	Montreal, Canada
March 7-10, 2021	International Federation of Genetics Societies Meeting	Cape Town, South Africa
October 19 - 23, 2021	ASHG Meeting	Montreal, Canada

Table 7: CINECA targeted conferences

6 Training plan

In the initial phase of the project, most training activities will be internal; the different CINECA work packages have many interdependencies, and members from one WP will need to be trained in the use of the outputs produced by other work packages.

WP6 will facilitate inter-WP staff visits upon request of CINECA project members. After a staff visit, the involved parties are required to contribute a blog post about their activities and the outcome as a success story. As the project progresses, the focus of training activities will shift from internal knowledge exchange to dissemination of CINECA outcomes to the wider stakeholder community.

WP6 will coordinate training activities, design and deliver strategy in collaboration with all WPs. Thus, each scientific/technical WP has dedicated resource and associated milestones to deliver training materials for inclusion in the outputs of WP6. The milestones will not only guarantee the involvement of the technical work packages in outreach, dissemination and training but also bring the project partners closer to their external stakeholders. The formal milestones will ensure that input from the technical work package are clear and trackable. WP6 will provide guidance in the creation of these materials by collaborating with the technical work packages.

Work package	Delivery month
WP3 - Cohort Level Meta Data Representation	12
WP5 - Healthcare Interoperability and Clinical Applications	12
WP1 - Federated Data Discovery and Querying	36
WP2 - Interoperable Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure	36
WP7 - Ethical and legal governance framework for transnational data-sharing	36
WP4 - Federated Joint Cohort Analysis	48

Table 8: Training content deliverable dates for CINECA WPs

As expected, the content delivery is predominantly in the second-half of the project as it is linked to the technical project deliverables; this is also why the early emphasis in the CINECA training programme is on webinars and staff visit programme, from the second year of the project we will start to add face-to-face courses as well as hackathons/knowledge exchange events, but the majority of the face-to-face events will take place in the second half of the project.

We will consider the competencies required by our stakeholder community; where training already exists to fulfil competency requirements, we will make this transparent; this will enable us to focus on developing novel training, and to build the technical outputs of the project into this training as the project progresses. Involvement of the technical and ELSI work packages (WP1-7) will be crucial for this. Training will be delivered by appropriate means for the level of competence required. This may range from short, standalone learning interventions such as webinars or online tutorials (good for

immediate training needs and for general awareness training), to longer interventions such as immersive face-to-face courses or mini secondments, which are better for developing advanced skills.

6.1 Webinars and short videos

The CINECA webinar series aims to discuss ways to address common challenges and share best practices in the field of cohort data analysis, as well as distribute CINECA project results. All CINECA webinars include an audience question and answer session during which attendees can ask questions and make suggestions. All CINECA webinars are recorded and uploaded to the CINECA YouTube channel, in addition the videos are embedded on the CINECA website (<https://www.cineca-project.eu/webinars>).

The first CINECA webinar took place on Thursday 6 June 2019, Thomas Keane the CINECA coordinator introduced the CINECA project. The first webinar also marked the completion of milestones 6.2 - First training intervention delivered.

All CINECA work package leaders are encouraged to communicate their submitted deliverables in the form of a webinars. In addition, we will add guest webinars from related organisations to highlight the research landscape that CINECA belongs to, as well as webinars to address fundamental concept and the identified training needs areas (e.g. data harmonisation, data security).

In collaboration with WP3 (training content delivery milestone 3.4 - see Table 8), we will be producing short videos (~ 5-7 min elevator pitches), covering concepts and tools related to cohort level meta data representation. For the month 12 milestone, two pilot videos will be created, one on ontologies and one on the semantic tool suite. The short videos are a useful training resources in their own right, especially for general awareness training but can also be used as an outreach tool for WP6 to interest the CINECA community in more in-depth training and as a resource list that could be sent out to training participants in advance of a face-to-face training event. Depending on the topic the short videos could be linked to more in-depth webinars later in the project.

After the pilot videos have been produced, the technical work packages (including the ELSI work packages) will be invited to contribute to the series. The videos will be accessible through the CINECA YouTube channel and embedded on the CINECA website, our newsletter and social media channels will be used to promote the existence of the videos.

6.2 Staff visit programme

Early training activities will be primarily focused on interworkpackage knowledge exchanges, to facilitate alignment of activities between different WPs. As a first step, inter-WP dependencies were elucidated from the individual work package plans presented at the CINECA kickoff meeting. Based on these dependencies and input from work package leads, a rough timeline of useful staff visits over the course of CINECA lifetime was created.

Staff visits must occur across different WPs and must involve European partners as the visiting party. WP members will be able to request staff visits through an online application form (<https://forms.gle/Nga8BdJ8sRCrQELPA>), to be approved by WP6 members. A motivation for the staff visit and an estimate of cost will need to be submitted as part of the application.

Staff visit costs will be processed using a overclaim/underclaim method, where the visitor's institute will overclaim budget from the EC and EMBL-EBI will underclaim budget. These budget adjustments will be processed at either open amendment sessions or at the end of the reporting period. A cost declaration form will need to be completed by the visitor's financial contact after the staff visit, no later than 6 weeks after the visit to determine the full cost of the visit. Visitor reimbursement and/or booking travel & accommodation will be the responsibility of the visitor's institute. Costs declared have to be in line with the expense guidelines at the visitor's institute

After the staff exchange, participating parties are required to contribute a blog post describing the visit and its outcomes, suitable for publication on the CINECA website as a success story. Furthermore, both the visiting and hosting party will be asked to fill in a feedback survey and participate in long-term impact assessment surveys 6-12 months and 18-24 months after the staff visit.

The first staff exchange expected around the second half of 2019 are shown below:

Visiting Partner	Hosting Partner	Motivation	Time
ELIXIR Czech Republic	WP2	Integration of CanDIG with ELIXIR AAI	Q4 2019
WP5 (EMC)	WP2	Integration of AAI (Milestone M5.1)	Q4 2019 / Q1 2020
EMBL-EBI (EGA/UK Biobank)	ELIXIR Finland	Integration of EGA with CanDIG and ELIXIR AAI	Q3 or Q4 2019

Table 9: Scheduled CINECA staff visit programme

6.3 Training events

As stated above, the training content produced by the technical work packages is predominantly planned for delivery in the second-half of the project as it is linked to the technical project deliverables; this is also why the early emphasis in the CINECA training programme is on webinars and staff visit programme, from the second year of the project we will start to add face-to-face courses as well as hackathons/knowledge exchange events, but the majority of the face-to-face events will take place in the second half of the project, therefore planning of face-to-face training events will gather speed after the first year of the project.

6.3.1 Topics for face-to-face training events in 2020

- Galaxy Workshop. Galaxy (<https://galaxyproject.org/>) is a web-based biomedical analysis platform used in WP5 for clinical applications. The workshop will be a multi-day event covering

1) a general introduction to the Galaxy platform, and 2) in-depth tutorials covering one or more of the analysis pipelines developed in WP5 (e.g. microbiota analysis for clinical diagnostics). All materials will be made available on the Galaxy training materials framework (<https://training.galaxyproject.org>) and are designed to be suitable for both face-2-face and online delivery. A F2F workshop is planned in Q3/Q4 of 2020, and we will explore the possibilities of additional online or hybrid workshops in order to reach a wider audience.

- Knowledge exchange event covering the basic concepts of ELIXIR? AAI (Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure), federated access and lessons learned from ELIXIR? AAI integration of cohorts; best practice and use cases on the implementing of ELIXIR? AAI - potentially in collaboration with ELIXIR. 2020 or 2021 depending on status of cohort integration.
- Data life cycle; including concepts of biocuration, cohort meta data, data standard, FAIR principles and data harmonisation. This topic was highlighted a number of times during the IHCC stakeholder session as an urgent need across many cohorts.

6.3.2 *Topics for face-to-face training events in the second half of the project (2021 & 2022)*

- Federated data analysis course, incorporating tools, standards and use cases resulting from the technical work packages
 - This will likely be in year 4, though we will explore whether a “leaky pipeline” course is feasible in year 3 and if it could potentially be used to provide feedback and additional user input to the technical work packages
- ELSI standards

7 Impact

WP6 has identified the following potential impact:

On the CINECA consortium

- By involving the technical work packages in outreach, dissemination and training we bring project partners closer to their external stakeholders
- Each technical work package has a milestone that feeds into WP6, ensuring that inputs are clear and trackable

On external stakeholders

- By providing opportunities for collaboration
- By providing new training opportunities and raising awareness of existing ones
- Potential for impact on all stakeholder groups, e.g. the researchers leading and implementing international cohort projects; cohort participants; clinical practitioners working with cohort participants to translate genomics research into clinical decisions; those managing the data and metadata collected; those providing the systems that enable this collection, the funders of such projects and others providing related education and outreach

Visibility of the CINECA project will be promoted by WP6 through surveys, workshops, training events, website, social media, conferences and promotion of CINECA publications.

We will monitor the impact of our outreach and training activities both immediately after each activity and in the longer term, through surveys and, where appropriate, structured interviews with representative stakeholders.

For training activities, we will make use of ELIXIR's harmonised procedure for monitoring short and medium-term impact. This includes a core set of survey questions immediately after completion of a course, which provides information on the quality of the training and the extent to which the trainees' expectations were met by the course. A second set of questions, sent approximately 6 months to a year after completion of the course, attempts to ascertain the impact of the training on the trainees' work, including collaborations, publications and new positions influenced by the training received. Adoption of this framework, which essentially amounts to a minimum standard for monitoring the impact of a training intervention, does not preclude us from asking project-specific questions. We might, for example, want to ask our trainees whether CINECA courses have enabled them to identify new associations, incorporate studies that they previously couldn't access, or perform statistical analyses that previously weren't sufficiently highly powered. Training events are also an excellent opportunity to gather constant input on our stakeholder analysis and to monitor whether the bottlenecks faced by scientists analysing their cohort data stay static or evolve throughout the lifetime of the CINECA project. For the long-term impact assessment of the staff visits, both the visiting and hosting party will be asked to fill in a feedback survey directly after the event and participate in long-term impact assessment surveys 6-12 months and 18-24 months after the staff visit.

The long-term impact analysis of dissemination and outreach is less well established compared to the training impact analysis. We are tracking analytics on our website as well as social media channels to analyse our reach. By tracking the events that CINECA project partners are involved in we can in addition estimate how many users we reach in the various research communities. However, these are often relatively static measurements, they are capable of analysing if our outreach activities are being carried out effectively and whether our reach is increasing but are maybe not very apt at analysing what long-term impact our outreach and dissemination activities have on our community. In collaboration with other international initiatives (incl. ELIXIR) we would like to explore potential strategies and best practices to analyse the impact of our outreach and dissemination strategy.

8 Conclusion & future work

Future efforts in social media will include:

- With the firm establishment of twitter, shift the primary focus to LinkedIn
- Evaluate the potential of introducing Facebook based on demand

The training plan will continue to be refined over the next 3 months, with training events for 2020 confirmed. An updated plan will be given in D6.2 Training programme in month 12, where we will also report on the status of the planned staff visits and webinar series.

9 Abbreviations

AAI	: Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure
BBMRI	: Biobanking and BioMolecular Resources Research Infrastructure
CORBEL	: Coordinated Research Infrastructures Building Enduring Life-science Services
EC	: European Commission
ELSI	: Ethical, Legal and Social Issues
F2F	: Face to Face
ICGC	: International Cancer Genome Consortium
IHCC	: International HundredK+ Cohort Consortium
ISCB	: International Society for Computational Biology
RFI	: Request for Information
WP	: Work Package